

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

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No. 29

• Costa Rica

Alexandrium monilatum (Howell) Balech bloom in the Gulf of Nicoya, Puntarenas

The Gulf of Nicoya, an estuary on the Pacific coast of Costa Rica, extends 80 Km, from the Tempisque River to the Pacific, with a maximum width of 50 Km at the mouth, and an area of 1550 Km². Hydrography of the Gulf depends on rainfall and wind patterns. Nutrient advection into the Gulf, during the rainy season (May to November) carried by the Grande de Tárcoles and Tempisque Rivers [1], have a stimulant effect on phytoplankton abundance [1-3] and composition [4].

The Gulf of Nicoya is a very important fishing ground on the Pacific coast. About 800 families make their living from shellfish extraction in the Gulf. The Gulf waters and the surrounding mangroves are also important nursery areas for larvae and juveniles of commercially

important species, and many beach areas have intense tourist activity. Therefore, harmful algal blooms pose a threat to the Gulf resources, fisheries, consumer health, the incipient aquaculture activity and tourism.

Phytoplankton blooms have been documented for the Gulf since 1954. However, the identification of the causative organisms started in 1980 when the organism responsible for a red bloom that affected the entire Pacific coast of Costa Rica was found to be *Cochlodinium catenatum* Okamura [5]. Red tides dominated by *C. catenatum* have been common in the Gulf, along with blooms of *Mesodinium rubrum* Lohmann. Other potentially harmful species of dino-

Fig. 1. Antapical view of *A. monilatum*, showing the characteristic pore plate with a large pore and radiating striae. From the September bloom in the Gulf of Nicoya, Costa Rica.

(Cont'd on p.2)

Newly formed Korean Harmful Algal Bloom Research Group (KORHAB)

Huge damage to fisheries by HABs occurs every year in Korea. In 2001, Korean researchers met during the 2nd international HAB meeting at the National Fisheries Research & Development Institute (NFRDI) in Busan, Korea to discuss, and to form the Korean Harmful Algal Bloom Research Group (KORHAB). Eventually, KORHAB was organized at the first official HAB meeting in Hanyang University on June 17, 2005, with the participation of over 100 researchers from Universities, Research Institutes and relevant agencies. The ac-

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Fig. 2. Long chains and solitary cells of *A. monilatum* (light microphotographs of Lugol's stained cells) from the September bloom in the Gulf of Nicoya, Costa Rica.

flagellates reported for the Gulf were *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum*, *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *Alexandrium catenella*, and *A. monilatum* [6].

Alexandrium monilatum has been found associated with other bloom organisms in the Gulf but, even when it reached high concentrations, was never previously the dominant organism [6]. But since August 27, 2005, a greenish coloured bloom has been developing, and *A. monilatum* is the most abundant organism present. Solitary cells as well as chains up to 108 cells long were observed (Fig. 2). Water samples collected off the Puntarenas peninsula, on August 31st, at depths of 1, 5 and 10 m, showed concentrations of 4.95×10^5 cells/L (99.5% *A. monilatum*), 2.6×10^5 cells/L (98.1% of *A. monilatum*) and 7.2×10^3 cells/L (55.4% of *A. monilatum*) respectively. Other dinoflagellates accompanying this bloom were species from the genus *Ceratium* and *Prorocentrum*. Surface water samples from Isla Jesucita showed maximum concentrations of 4.3×10^5

Table 1. Dinoflagellate concentration (cells/L and % of total number), at the Puntarenas dock, ($9^{\circ} 58' 025''$ N and $84^{\circ} 49' 769''$ W), Gulf of Nicoya, Costa Rica, 02 September 2005.

Species	Depth					
	1m		5m		8m	
	cells/L	%	cells/L	%	cells/L	%
<i>A. monilatum</i>	2,053,000	98.4	325,000	82.3	96,500	95
<i>P. bahamense</i> var. <i>compressum</i>	17,000	0.81	3,500	0.9	0	0
<i>G. catenatum</i>	3,000	0.14	61,000	15.5	1,000	1
<i>G. splendens</i>	6,000	0.30	2,500	0.6	500	0.5
<i>C. catenatum</i>	1,000	0.05	0	0	500	0.5

cells/L.

Water sampling was repeated on September 2nd at the Puntarenas dock and *A. monilatum* continued to be the most abundant species. However, other toxic dinoflagellates were observed as well (Table 1).

Surface water samples collected on September 09, south of the Puntarenas peninsula ($09^{\circ}55'78''$; $84^{\circ}48'08''$), showed a maximum concentration of 3.2×10^6 cells/L.

During the sampling periods, salinity ranged from 29 to 30‰ and temperature from 30 to 31.5°C.

In areas where concentrations were below 5×10^5 cells/L, water was greenish-grey in colour but, when concentrations were higher, water colour turned olive green. This bloom produced cream or beige colour foam at the tidal break line. Skin contact with the water during sampling in bloom areas produced intense itching, far more intense than the itching produced during sampling of *C. catenatum* blooms.

Alexandrium monilatum produces ichthyotoxin that has not been found to accumulate in filter feeding shellfish [7, 8], but is however lethal to many animals [9]. It is a warm water species that has been reported from the Gulf of México, the Caribbean, Venezuela and the Pacific coast of Ecuador [8, 10]. Juhl

[9] indicates that it requires a high N cell quota which can help explain the rareness of the blooms in the Gulf of Nicoya since phytoplankton in the Gulf is N-limited during the rainy season [2, 4] when growth conditions are optimal in terms of water temperature and salinity.

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companying photo shows the first KORHAB organizing committee elected. Official meetings will be convened twice a year regularly with three special lectures by invited speakers and presentations by KORHAB members.

The main purpose of this group is to provide a unique atmosphere in collaboration and in sharing information between Korean researchers in various HAB related studies in biology, oceanography, fisheries, and limnology. To take advantage of the existing international HAB related societies, such as GEOHAB, SCOR, APEC and ICES, KORHAB will actively cooperate to de-

velop local and international HAB related research projects. In 2006, KORHAB will coordinate an "International Workshop for *Cochlodinium* Researches" to be held in Korea, sponsored by the Korean Ministry of Maritime Affairs & Fisheries (MOMAF) and NOAA of USA. KORHAB will also provide information and counsel on HAB related matters to local and international communities.

The Korean government will give full support to KORHAB activities. Currently the KORHAB office is located in NFRDI, Busan, Korea.

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• Egypt

Toxic phytoplankton species linked to massive invertebrate and fish mortality in the Eastern Harbour of Alexandria

The coastal area of Alexandria is highly eutrophic due to direct discharges of wastewater, mainly from two land-based sources, estimated as about $7 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$ of agricultural drainage water mixed with the overflow from Lake Mariout (main basin outfalls: about $500 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$ primary treated and $300 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$ untreated municipal waste water) into Mex Bay, west of Alexandria, and about $2 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$ of industrial and agricultural waste water into Abu Qir Bay to the east.

The Eastern Harbour (E.H.) of Alexandria is located in the central part of the city. It is a sheltered, relatively shallow semi-enclosed marine basin. It was a recipient of huge amounts of municipal wastewater during the last three decades. Yet, it is encouraging in that remedial actions have been taken by the Alexandria Governorate to close the E.H. outfalls, as well as the main sewer of Alexandria (Kayet Bey) at its western vicinity, and their share of waste water had been diverted to the Lake after primary treatment. However, due to water circulation, the harbour is still affected by the water discharge, mainly from Mex Bay (8 Km long).

During August 2004 and July-August 2005, incidents of fish and invertebrate mortality occurred accompanying long duration of visible water discoloration.

According to information received from marine protection and diving organizations, the authority of Alexandria Governorate and the environmental authority, "marine life on the bottom of the E.H. were severely destroyed. Dead fish and stunned demersal and pelagic fishes losing their equilibrium, gasping at the surface, swimming either on their sides or upside down, suffering from disorientation and unresponsiveness to human presence, and the presence of hundreds of small crabs found dead on the sand beach or seen migrating towards the beach at dawn or found dead in fishermens nets indicating signs of toxicity". Symptoms of anoxic conditions were also observed in dead fish, including yellowish coloration of the body and gills.

The last cases of massive invertebrate and fish mortality occurred in the harbour during October 1994 [1], caused by *Alexandrium minutum* with evidence of toxicity, and during 1998-2000 attributed to the first occurrence of *Gymnodinium mikimotoi* ($0.93 \times 10^6 \text{ cell l}^{-1}$ on 11 August 1999, $1.8 \times 10^6 \text{ cell l}^{-1}$ on 30 May 2000, and *Chattonella antiqua* ($0.85 \times 10^6 \text{ cell l}^{-1}$ on 27 July 1999, $1.14 \times 10^6 \text{ cell l}^{-1}$ on 21 May 2000 [2]. The blooms in 1999-2000 were transferred to the harbour from Mex Bay (a highly eutrophic bay), through the ide-

alized pattern of a biological spreading, neighborhood diffusion, since hydrographic processes must be responsible. However, the present blooms during August 2004 and July-August 2005 originated from the Eastern Harbour. Twentyfour species, monospecific or in combination, gradually increased in the neritic waters of Alexandria, and their intensity and geographical extent seem to be on rise; the phenomenon is now of regular occurrence in the warm seasons. Ten of them were recorded toxic [3].

During these blooms, surface water temperatures were from 27.5°C to $>30^\circ\text{C}$, and salinity values low ($34.6\text{-}37.5 \text{ psu}$), affected by discharged water from the west. Reduced salinity seems to contribute to the development of *C. antiqua* and *G. mikimotoi* in the harbour [4]. A stable water column is a permanent characteristic feature. Nutrient concentrations are generally relatively low, while the reverse is the case for the organic matter.

G. catenatum Graham became noticeable on 3 August 2004 ($0.15 \times 10^6 \text{ cell l}^{-1}$), under relatively high nutrient concentrations ($1.68 \mu\text{M PO}_4^{3-}$, $3.65 \mu\text{M NO}_3^-$, $3.8 \mu\text{M NH}_4^+$), and low organic matters (1.46 mg l^{-1}), and was followed by its major peak on 7 August, and less so on the next day. Phosphate and nitrate concentration were reduced to a

Table 1. Species linked to massive invertebrate and fish mortality in the Eastern Harbour of Alexandria during 2004-2005

Species	Year/Maximum Density (M. D)			
	2004	M. D	2005	M. D
<i>Alexandrium ostenfeldii</i>	9 August 14-15 21	0.11x10 ⁶ about 0.32x10 ⁶ 0.51x 10 ⁶	23 – 24-25 July 1 August	0.13x10 ⁶ , 0.14x10 ⁶ and 0.52x10 ⁶ , respectively 0.082x10 ⁶
<i>Chattonella antiqua</i>	21 August	1.26x10 ⁶	25 July 13-14 August	0.16x10 ⁶ 0.33x10 ⁶ – 0.49x10 ⁶
<i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i>	7-8 August 15 August 17 21	2.73x10 ⁶ , 1.53x10 ⁶ , respectively 1.6x10 ⁶ 0.99x10 ⁶ 1.34x10 ⁶	21 July 28 30 3 August 8 10 14	0.38x10 ⁶ 0.33x10 ⁶ 0.56x10 ⁶ 0.58x10 ⁶ 0.62x10 ⁶ 0.78x10 ⁶ 0.62x10 ⁶
<i>Gymnodinium mikimotoi</i>	13 August	0.16x10 ⁶	30 July 10-11 August 14	0.06x10 ⁶ 1.17x10 ⁶ – 1.92x10 ⁶ 0.73x10 ⁶

third on 8 August (0.18 μM PO_4^{3-} and 0.55 μM NO_3^-), ammonia was almost unchanged (3.81 μM and 3.47 μM , for the two days, respectively). These two peaks accompanied high levels of organic matter concentrations (7.5 and 8 mg l^{-1}). *G. catenatum* was found in Alexandria waters in 1992 [5, 6].

Alexandrium ostenfeldii (Paulsen) Balech *et* Tangen was first found west of Alexandria (Mex Bay) during 1992 [7], and in the Eastern Harbour during 1998 [2]. Its maximum density on 25 July 2005, in combination with other species, raised Chl. *a* content to 59.5 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$. Phosphate was at 0.62 μM , nitrate 1.62 μM and ammonia 4.18 μM . *Gymnodinium mikimotoi* Miya *et* Kominami *ex* Oda was previously recorded in the E.H. of Alexandria during September 1998 at 22.5-27.2°C and salinity of 34-36.5 psu [2]. Densities between 0.13x10⁶ and 1.66x10⁶ cell l⁻¹ were found from late September–early October 2000 [8]. *Chattonella antiqua* (Hada) Ono attained increased density on 19 August, reaching a peak two days later, accompanied Chl. *a* at 65 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$. Its densities during 2005 were significantly lower than those recorded in the same period during 2004. *C. antiqua* was first described and recently founded in the Eastern Harbour to be most frequently at 24.5-26°C and 34.5-35 psu, and it shared a role in the 3 killing blooms during 2001 [4].

It is concluded that:

1- The water characteristics were deeply affected by water discharge from the west. A reduction in the discharged water is urgently required to improve the situation, not only in the harbour, but also along the whole coast of Alexandria.

2- The severe damage to marine life in the Eastern Harbour of Alexandria during August 2004 and July-August 2005 was a direct impact of the occurrence of 6 toxic phytoplankton species.

3- The long duration of the bloom during the whole of August could have amplified this dramatic event.

4- The sever consumption of inorganic nutrients signals their importance. However, high organic matter concentrations could help maintenance of the blooms.

5- Recurrent blooms are expected in the following years.

6- The rare occurrence of undesirable species such as *Alexandrium minutum*, *Pseudo-nitzschia pungens* and *Heterosigma* sp. could inflict more damage in the near future.

7- A monitoring programme must be carried out along the Egyptian Mediterranean coast to evaluate the real situation. Human health is placed at risk, ecosystems are altered, fishing and aquaculture suffer economic losses.

This communication is part of the monitoring program carried out in Alexandria waters for 143 days between July 2004 and October 2005.

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• Spain

First detection of diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia brasiliiana* (non toxic) and its relative *P. multistriata* (presumably toxic) in the NW Mediterranean Sea

Diatoms of the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* are widely distributed in seas and oceans. They attract world wide interest since they were found to produce the lethal neurotoxin domoic acid (DA). Back in 1987, a member of this genus (*P. multiseries*) caused amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP) in eastern Canada [1]. Production of DA is reported for at least ten species of *Pseudo-nitzschia* [2], and their blooms result in marked toxin accumulation through the food chains, with subsequent impacts on individual marine organisms, total ecosystems, humans, and even the economy [3]. In the Mediterranean, both *Pseudo-nitzschia galaxiae* and *P. multistriata* were shown to be toxic [4].

Since 1995, a continuous phytoplankton monitoring programme is carried out along the NE coast of the Spanish province of Catalonia. The region has a 400 km coastline, is densely populated, and contains many harbours (on average one per 10 km). These artificial structures provide suitable niches for organisms whose growth depends on nutrient-rich (semi-)confined conditions. During 2004 bucket samples were taken from 16 of these harbours and aliquots (150 ml) were preserved with Lugol's iodine solution. Samples were analysed with SEM and TEM techniques allowing identification of the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* at the species level using their known morphological characteristics.

The most abundant *Pseudo-nitzschia* species recorded were *P. delicatissima*, *P. calliantha*, *P. multistriata* and recently *P. brasiliiana*. The latter was first recorded off Cubelles beach (September 2004), with cell densities up to (2.8×10^5 cells L^{-1}). The species was, however, not dominant (30% of total *Pseudo-nitzschia* population) and co-existed with *P. calliantha* (30%), *P. delicatissima* (30%), and *P. fraudulentata* (10%). In September 2005,

P. brasiliiana was found to dominate (95.2%) the *Pseudo-nitzschia* population in Vilanova harbour (2.5×10^5 cells L^{-1}). To our knowledge, this species has not previously been reported from the Mediterranean Sea. Our measurements revealed an apical axis length from 23.41 to 39.4 μm ($n=30$), and a transapical axis length from 2.34 to 3.79 μm . These values coincide with those of the original description [5]. The raphe is extremely eccentric and not interrupted by a central nodule. The fibulae and the interstriae are regularly spaced, 20-26 in 10 μm . The interstriae contain two rows of poroids with a tendency for three. On 1 September 2005, *P. multistriata* was dominant (100%) in Tarragona port, with densities up to 4×10^6 cells L^{-1} . Cells of this species were isolated from this bloom and HPLC pigment analyses of the clonal culture obtained revealed Chl *a*, four polar chlorophyll *c* pigments, 6 carotenes and several degradation compounds.

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• Mexico

Is *Pseudo-nitzschia pseudodelicatissima* toxin the principal cause of sardines, dolphins, sea lions and pelicans mortality in 2004 in Mexico?

Fig. 1. Map with localization of events reported here: Caborca, Sonora in January 2004 and Mazatlán, Sinaloa in July 2004.

On 13 January, 2004, 79 long beaked dolphins (*Delphinus capensis*) stranded at Bahía La Salada, in San Jorge Bay, Caborca, Sonora (31°03'54''N, 113°07'51''W) [1]. Fishermen reported several tons of sardines floating dead on the open sea during the first half of January (Fig. 1). The total counts of affected animals included 112 dolphins (103 long beaked *Delphinus*

Table 1. Phytoplankton composition of samples taken in Mazatlán Bay (July 8, 2004).

Species	Cell number / ml	% total
<i>P. pseudodelicatissima</i>	3921	67.0
<i>P. subfraudulenta</i>	929	15.9
<i>Gymnodinium</i> sp.	825	14.1
<i>Protoperidinium quinquecorne</i>	138	2.4
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	17	0.3
<i>Coscinodiscus</i> sp.	10	0.2
Total	5840	100

capensis, 9 common dolphins *Delphinus delphis*), 195 sea lions (*Zalophus californianus*) and 9 grey pelicans (*Pelecanus occidentalis*), plus 20 tons of sardines (*Sardinops* spp.) [2]. LCMS analyses of blood samples collected from live or recently dead stranded dolphins detected domoic acid (311-312 *m/z*) in three of the four samples tested. LCMS-MS of ions captured at 311-312 *m/z* and fragmented, produced daughter ions of 266-267 *m/z* in all four samples, a characteristic degradation product of domoic acid (Fig. 2). Unfortunately, no plankton samples were taken or analyzed at the time of the event. Climatological data presented the same image found during previous *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* blooms in the area and depicts a recurrent pattern of events that may help to predict occurrences (to be published elsewhere).

Discolorations were observed in Mazatlán Bay, Sinaloa, Mexico (23°13'N, 106°2'W) during July 5-11,

2004. Samples collected the 8th and 13th were observed by inverted LM [3]. Results indicated the dominance of the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* (Table 1), although the color was caused by an unidentified gymnodinoid and *Protoperidinium quinquecorne* (Fig. 3).

Even when discoloration vanished on the 11th, samples from day 13th had 4850 cells/ml of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. as isolated cells and in pairs. *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. cells present in the sample were analyzed by SEM and TEM and the most abundant species was identified as *P. pseudodelicatissima* (67% dominance of the total phytoplankton) (Fig. 4a-f). Although characteristics observed corresponded to *P. pseudodelicatissima* (Table 2), some differences were noted. There is a thickening of the middle portion (Fig. 4d) and the poroids present a membrane less fragmented than that shown on ICES leaflets [4], but similar to that shown by Lundholm *et al.*, [5], divided in two main portions; also, in the central part, there are two smaller poroids (Fig. 4e-f). *Pseudo-nitzschia* cf. *americana* (Fig. 4g-h), was infrequently observed and was not quantified. In the last species, the observed poroids showed non-fragmented hymens (Fig. 4h), but in the larger ones it is possible

Table 2. Morphometrical characteristics of the taxa discussed in the text.

Features	<i>P. pseudodelicatissima</i>	<i>P. subfraudulenta</i>	<i>P. cf. americana</i>
Valve view	Linear	spline shaped	linear
Chain overlap	1/6	¼	?
Apical axis in µ	64 – 94	52-72	20
Trans-apical axis in µ	1.5-2.0	4.2-5.4	1.7-2.5
Striae in 10 µ	38-47	36-	30-40
Interstriae in 10 µ	40	19-20	14
Rows of poroids	1	2	2
Poroids in 1 µ	4	5-6	5
Poroids fragmentation	2	2-5	0
Fibulae in 10 µ	22-26	15-20	22-30
Central interspace	+	+	-

Fig.2. Graphs of LCMS-MS of blood samples collected from stranded dolphins (January 2004). Samples were cleaned-up by SPEC before HPLC analyses.

to appreciate a poly-fragmentation, suggesting that the size of the pore determines the fragmentation of the hymen (see white arrowheads on Fig. 4g). *P. subfraudulenta* (16% dominance of the total phytoplankton) was also found (Fig. 5a-f). This species shows wide variations of the fragmentation present on the cingular band, evidence of contiguous poroids (Fig. 5e-e').

Previous *Pseudonitzschia* sp. blooms have not been detected due to the fact that they did not discolor the waters, even though Mazatlán Bay has been monitored frequently since 1979 [6]. Nevertheless, domoic acid has been detected and reported previously in the Gulf of California [7, 8] and *P. australis* mentioned as responsible. The correct identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species in the Mexican Pacific has not been deeply pursued in recent years. Hernández-Becerril identified 5 species and among them, reported the toxic spe-

cies *P. australis* outside the Gulf of California [9], while inside the Gulf its presence is uncertain. This is the first documented report of the presence of the toxic species *P. pseudodelicatissima* in the Gulf of California. Previously, Gomez-Aguirre *et al.* [10] mentioned the species but the poly-fragmented hymen shown on their figures (6 a-c) is closer to *P. calliantha* [5], showed to segregate as a completely different clade by molecular analysis of its ITS1, 5.8S, and ITS'' of the nuclear encoded rRNA [5]. Nevertheless, identifications based on the size, structure and fragmentation of the hymen may require further review in that, as shown here, the poroids present on the cingular band of *P. subfraudulenta* show wide variations of the fragmentation pattern: 2-3-4-6 fragments (Fig. 5e-e').

In Mazatlán, ten dead brown peli-

Fig.4. *Pseudo-nitzschia pseudodelicatissima* and *P. americana*. a-b) *P. pseudodelicatissima* cells, valve view, SEM (a), TEM (b), (scale 10 μm). c) Central inter-space, TEM (scale 0.5 μm). d) Widened middle region (arrowheads), TEM. (scale 1 μm). e-f) Poroids in girdle band showing bifragmented hymen, TEM (scale 1 μm). g) *P. americana* cells in valve view, major pore showing poly-fragmentation (white arrowhead). h) Detail of poroids showing non-fragmented and bi-fragmented ones.

Fig.3. Plankton species found in water samples collected July 8th in Mazatlán Bay: a) Peridinoid; b) Gymnodinium sp; c) *P. subfraudulenta*; d) *P. pseudodelicatissima*.

cans (*Pelecanus occidentalis californiensis*) as well as fish from several species were found on July 17th, and the number of affected animal increased during the following days. Health Authorities looked for the causes but toxin analyses were not carried out. The toxin analysis of a bottle sample of the bloom revealed a toxin profile similar to that found in the blood of dolphins stranded in previous months (Fig. 2) [1]. Nevertheless, the lag time between both events (Caborca, Son. and Mazatlan, Sin.) and the differences between the samples obtained during them, do not allow us to establish the cause of death of the animals found nearby Mazatlan which were not analyzed for toxins. The evident lack of coordination of actions developed to

Fig. 5. *Pseudo-nitzschia subfraudulenta* a) Valve view, SEM (scale 10 μm). b) Central inter-space, external side, SEM. c) Central interspace, internal side, SEM. d) Central inter-space, internal side, TEM (scale for b, c & d 1 μm). e-e') Poroids in girdle band showing different fragmentation patterns (scale 0.2 μm). f) Valve view, TEM (scale 10 μm).

attend these events is responsible for the absence of strong arguments about the causes and frequency of these events, which can pass undetected or unexplained even when the coastal fauna is severely affected.

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•Denmark

Domoic acid in Danish blue mussels due to a bloom of *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata*

In March and April 2005, a bloom of the pennate diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* resulted in accumulation of domoic acid (DA) in blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) to levels above the EU-regulatory limit of 20 mg kg⁻¹. Domoic acid is a potent neurotoxic amino acid that has previously caused Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) in humans after consumption of contaminated mussels from Atlantic Canada [1]. In the recent Danish incident, no human illnesses were reported, but as a precaution the mussel fishery was either conditionally open with intensified surveillance or closed for five weeks at various sites in Denmark. The Danish bloom probably originated north of

Fig. 1. Concentration of *P. seriata* cells in the water column and of domoic acid in blue mussels during spring 2005 in two areas in Danish coastal waters. A. East of Jutland. B. North of Funen.

Funen, a desirable area for mussel fishermen to collect mussels from natural shellfish banks. The highest concentra-

tion of *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* observed during the episode was 195,000 cells l⁻¹ and was detected on March 7th.

Fig. 2. Light micrograph of *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* chains.

At that time, DA was not measured, but a week later DA concentrations were 0.4 mg kg⁻¹ wet weight of mussels (Fig. 1). The *Pseudo-nitzschia* cell numbers decreased slightly until March 28 when DA in the mussels peaked at a concentration of 30 mg kg⁻¹. Two lots of blue mussels (each 27 tons) collected from a harvest area north of Funen on March 29th and 30th contained concentrations of 30 and 32 mg kg⁻¹, respectively, and were therefore discarded (Fig. 1). The bloom then declined in the waters north of Funen, but peaked further north on the east coast of Jutland. The peak of the bloom in that area was observed on April 3 at only 53,000 cells l⁻¹, but DA concentrations in the mussels reached 26 mg kg⁻¹.

During April, DA concentrations and cell numbers of *P. seriata* decreased, but on April 18th, mussels north of Funen still contained 12 mg DA kg⁻¹ and *P. seriata* concentrations were 23,000 cells l⁻¹. As determined by LC-MS, the total DA concentration in the water at that time was 0.49 ng ml⁻¹, corresponding to a concentration of 21 pg DA cell⁻¹ of *P. seriata*. This is a rather high cellular concentration but is within the range (0.31 to 33.6 pg DA cell⁻¹) found in laboratory growth experiments conducted on Danish strains [2]. Similar concentrations have been measured from Scottish and Canadian strains, which yielded DA concentrations of up to 14.7 pg cell⁻¹ and 7 pg cell⁻¹, respectively [3, 4].

In areas on the east coast of Jutland, the *P. seriata* bloom corresponded with the peak of DA in the mussels, whereas north of Funen, cell numbers seemed to

peak before DA accumulated in the mussels. The reasons for these apparent differences have not yet been determined, but might be due to the sampling procedure. The water samples for plankton analysis are aggregates of three sub-samples taken at different depths in the water column (surface, mid-water column, 1 m above bottom) in the harvest area. This aggregated sample may not be strictly representative of the actual plankton composition and concentration at the bottom of the water column where the benthic mussels were feeding, because the water column is often highly stratified in the harvest areas.

Relating the DA concentration to the concentration of *Pseudo-nitzschia* cells in the water column indicates that the action level of 200,000 *Pseudo-nitzschia* cells l⁻¹ that is currently used within the Danish monitoring program is too high for *P. seriata* under these circumstances (Fig. 1). Along the east coast of Jutland, cell concentrations increased to around 50,000 cells l⁻¹ simultaneously with DA concentrations rising to above the EU regulatory limit. A similar pattern was found in Atlantic Canada for this *Pseudo-nitzschia* species, where concentrations of 62,000 cells l⁻¹ occurred when DA in the mussels was above the regulatory limit [4]. An action limit below 50,000 cells l⁻¹ of *P. seriata* may also be valid for other countries where *Pseudo-nitzschia* cell concentrations

Fig. 3. *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata*, TEM micrograph showing the asymmetrical valve.

Fig. 4. *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata*, TEM micrograph of valve showing fibulae, interstriae and the special poroid arrangement.

serve as an early warning on whether or not DA monitoring is necessary. In any case, the interpretation of cell counts of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. as an index of impending toxicity in shellfish must be done cautiously. Certain strains of *P. seriata* from eastern Canada have been found to be non-toxic (Bates *et al.* 1989) and co-occurrence of toxic and non-toxic strains have also been recorded for many other *Pseudo-nitzschia* species.

The identification of *P. seriata* as the diatom responsible for the DA toxicity was confirmed by light and electron microscopy. *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* is morphologically close to *P. australis* and *P. seriata* f. *obtusata*, and in contrast to many other *Pseudo-nitzschia* species, all three taxa are more or less asymmetrical (Figs. 2, 3). *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* can be discriminated by the pointed tips in girdle view and by the poroid structure, with two rows of larger poroids, and one or two rows of smaller poroids in the middle (Fig. 4).

Pseudo-nitzschia seriata is a cold-water species that has been recorded from temperate and Arctic regions in the North Atlantic, but it is apparently absent from the north Pacific as well as from the southern hemisphere [5]. It is common in Scandinavian coastal waters, especially during spring. As far as we are aware, DA has only been detected in blue mussels at levels above the EU regulatory limit once before in Scandinavia - a sample from the west coast of Norway (Molde) in 2003 contained 23

mg kg⁻¹ (T. Aune, personal communication). We know that Danish cultures of *P. seriata* are able to produce DA, as cultures isolated from 1992 and later have been found toxic [2]. Why therefore have we not detected DA due to *P. seriata* in mussels before in Denmark? Monitoring results dating back to 1990 show that only one previous bloom of *Pseudo-nitzschia* was observed in spring (Year 2000), whereas blooms of other *Pseudo-nitzschia* species occur during summer in 8 of 13 years. Thus the bloom of *P. seriata* during spring 2005 can be characterized as an exceptional bloom. But note that domoic acid in mussels is measured only if mussel fishermen wish to harvest mussels and if cells of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. are observed; hence data on DA occurrence during spring is limited. We do not know why *P. seriata* was able to reach such high concentrations that it caused DA

accumulation in blue mussels. However, low water temperatures during February and March may have limited the growth of grazers (such as copepods) resulting in a lower grazing of *P. seriata*. This effect, combined with a rainy January and February, and much sunnier weather in March and April (up to 70% more than average) may have provided optimal bloom conditions for *P. seriata*.

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• Algeria

Detection of toxic *Gymnodinium catenatum* (Graham, 1943) in Algerian waters (SW Mediterranean Sea)

Gymnodinium catenatum is a naked chain and resting cyst forming dinoflagellate, known to produce toxins involved in PSP (Paralytic Shellfish Poi-

soning) events. *G. catenatum* was first described for the Gulf of California [1], but numerous studies in recent decades reveal a worldwide distribution of this

species. In Eastern Atlantic waters, it was first recorded in 1976 in samples from the NW coast of Spain [2]. In 1987, *G. catenatum* was identified as the causative species of an important PSP event along the Mediterranean coast of southern Spain [3] (Fig. 2). A continuous monitoring program, initiated in 1997, revealed the regular presence of *G. catenatum* in this area [4]. *G. catenatum* has also been detected along North Moroccan coasts [5], in the Algerian Basin, and in offshore waters near the Sardinia Channel [6] (Table 1). We present here the first report of a toxic *Gymnodinium catenatum* in Algerian coastal waters, detected in samples collected during several cruises in 1986 and 2001-2002. Sampling area and frequency are presented in Figure 3 and Table 1, respectively.

During the annual cycle of El Djamilia Bay between September 2001 and August 2002 (water temperatures 16.5 to 23.5 °C, salinity 36.5 to 36.9 psu, nitrate 0.08 to 0.59 $\mu\text{mole l}^{-1}$, phosphate 0.11-0.24 $\mu\text{mole l}^{-1}$, ammonium 0.01 to

Fig. 1. *Gymnodinium catenatum*: Light microscopic photographs of vegetative chains (a, b) and cyst (c) in field samples. Vegetative cell in culture (d). Vegetative chain in culture (e).

Table 1. Occurrences of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in the Mediterranean Sea: maximum concentrations, detection of toxicity and temporal distribution.

Max. Conc. Cells ⁻¹	Detection of toxicity	Month year	Location	Distance from the coast	Sampled periods	References
200		Sept. 1986	Cap Caxine	1.5-21 (miles)	Autumn-Spring 1986-1987	Present study
3000	Toxicity in shellfish	Febr.1989	Andalucia, Spain	Coastal waters	1987-1989	Bravo et al. 1990
10.000	Toxicity in shellfish	June 1995	Tetouan Region, Morocco		1992-1996 Monitoring	Tahri Joutei 1997
		Sept. 1999	Alboran Sea, Algerian Bassin Sardinia Strait	off-shore	1999 cruise	Gómez and Claustre 2001
34.000		July 2001	Andalucia, Spain	Coastal waters	1999-2002 Monitoring	Mamán et al. 2003
440		Sept. 2001	El-Djamila Bay	0.5	2001-2002 annual cycle	
2920		Oct. 2001	Algiers Bay	1	2001-2002 seasonal cruises	Present study
3200	Toxicity in a strain culture	Oct. 2001	Bou-Ismaïl Bay	1	2001-2002 seasonal cruises	

(miles)

0.04 $\mu\text{mole l}^{-1}$), *G. catenatum* was only detected in autumn, and showed low concentrations (<450 cells l^{-1}) at all times (Fig. 4). During the October 2001 cruise (water temperatures 18.5 to 23.5°C, salinity 36.7 to 37 psu, nitrate 0.27 to 1.16 $\mu\text{mole l}^{-1}$, phosphate 0.13-0.65 $\mu\text{mole l}^{-1}$, ammonium 0.01 to 0.07 $\mu\text{mole l}^{-1}$) high densities (maximum 3200 cells l^{-1} ; Table 1, Fig. 5) were detected in Algiers and Bou-Ismaïl Bays. Viable *G. catenatum* cysts (Fig 1) were isolated from sediment samples collected in January 2002 (50 m depth) in Bou-Ismaïl Bay. These cysts were employed to obtain clonal cultures of *G. catenatum*. HPLC analyses revealed a peridinin-containing pigment composition (Fig. 7a). These results closely resemble the *Alexandrium*-like composition [7] reported for *Gymnodinium aureolum* [8]. How-

ever, it strongly differed from those reported for the 19'-hexanoyloxyfucoxanthin and gyroxanthin-containing ichthiotoxic relatives *Gymnodinium* sp., *G. mikomitoi*, *G. breve* and *G. galatheanum* [8, 9, and papers cited there]. Additional HPLC analyses of the Algerian strain revealed a toxin composition (Fig. 7b) dominated by the relative low toxic C1 and C2 compounds (15 and 239 Mouse Units μMol^{-1} , respectively – see ref. 10). Only trace levels of the more toxic isomers GTX2 and GTX3 (892 and 1584 MU μMol^{-1}) were detected, and some unidentified compounds (possibly including dcGTX2/3). The strong dominance of the C-toxins was consistent with the absence of published records on *G. catenatum*-associated PSP events in Algerian waters. The toxin composition of

the strain analyzed more closely resembled that of Mediterranean analogues isolated from Andalucía (S Spain), than that of the (STX-containing) Atlantic representatives obtained from NW Spain [11]. However, all strains employed by the authors contained doSTX, and usually synthesized dcSTX, but these compounds remained below detection levels in our Algerian culture. Samples collected off Cape Caxine in September and October 1986 revealed the presence of *Gymnodinium catenatum* with concentrations lower than 250 cells l^{-1} (Fig. 6). During both periods *G. catenatum* co-existed with other potentially harmful species, including *Alexandrium* sp (chain-forming cells), *Dinophysis acuminata*, *Prorocentrum micans* and *Prorocentrum balticum*. Ours results show that *Gymnodinium catenatum* was already present in South-western Mediterranean waters prior to its first record in the Alboran Sea in 1987 [3]. Samples collected in November 2001 revealed the simultaneous presence of *G. catenatum* in coastal waters of both Algeria and Andalucía [4]. The presence of *G. catenatum* in the Mediterranean is nowadays restricted to the South Western Basin and seems to be associated with the Algerian Current, which flows from W to E along the north African coast as a continuation of the Almería-Oran Jet [12]. Molecular studies might elucidate possible relationships between the Algerian population and strains from other biogeographic regions. Harmful phyto-

Fig. 2. First detection of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in different regions of the Mediterranean Sea.

Fig. 3. Locations of the sampling stations in Algiers area.

Fig. 4. Annual distribution of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in El Djamilia Bay at 10m.

Fig. 5. Vertical distribution of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in Algiers and Bou-Ismaïl Bays during October 2001 cruise.

Fig. 6. Vertical distribution of *Gymnodinium catenatum* off Cape Caxine September 15th 1986.

plankton species are not yet continuously monitored in Algerian waters, even though associated intoxication events have been described for nearby regions [3, 5]. However, considering the regular presence of *G. catenatum* (and other harmful species) along the Algerian coast, its capability of synthesizing the toxic isomer pair GTX 2/3 and the wide range of additional compounds mentioned to occur in other strains, detailed studies on spatio-temporal distributions and their toxicity are most certainly recommended.

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Fig. 7. Absorbance and fluorescence chromatograms obtained with HPLC analysis of photosynthetic pigments and toxins present in extracts of a *Gymnodinium catenatum* strain isolated from Algerian coastal waters.

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•The Philippines

Fish Kills Associated with *Cochlodinium* Blooms in Palawan, The “Last Frontier” of the Philippines

Fig. 1. A) Map of Puerto Princesa, Palawan showing sampling sites where fish kills were observed: 1) Napsan, 2) Bagon Bayan, 3) Simpocan. B) Map of the Philippines showing bloom occurrence of *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*: 1) Iligan Bay, March 2002; 2) Balayan Bay, May 2002; 3) Puerto Princesa, March 2005.

Puerto Princesa, Palawan is considered as the “last ecological frontier” in the Philippines due to its vast yet relatively unexplored natural wonders. It is one of the marine biodiversity hot spots of the world, and contributes to the unprecedented biodiversity of the Sulu-Sulawesi Ecoregion, which is home to 400 coral species, and 650 reef fish species, among others. Even though Palawan (Fig. 1) is protected by Republic Act 7611 which stipulates sustainable development of its natural resources, the growing demand for its resources make it vulnerable to threats of over-fishing, dynamite fishing, coastal development and pollution. Metro Manila (the Philippines capital) relies on Palawan to provide 60% of its fish requirements, while 55% of the country’s total fish exports originate in Palawan.

A new threat, however, looms over Palawan’s fisheries.

In response to a call for help from the Mayor of Puerto Princesa, Palawan, Edward Hagedorn on 16 March 2005, a research team led by Dr. Rhodora V. Azanza of the Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines set out to investigate a fish kill in Puerto Princesa. Upon arrival in Puerto Princesa, a tech-

nical meeting with local government units was immediately held. The team, which included Jun Relox of the Central Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR), without delay, proceeded to Barangay Bagongbayan, Palawan to collect water samples which revealed a high concentration of the naked dinoflagellate, *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*. Barangays Simpocan and Napsan were also visited where dead fish were evident on the shore (Fig. 1A).

Prior to the investigation, fishermen were at a loss as to what has been causing fish kills in Palawan since January. According to the report of Zosima Jampit (Community Environment and Natural Resources Officer-Quezon, Palawan) to the Regional Director of Environmental Management Bureau, Department of Environment and Natural Resource, Mimaropa Region, fish kills were first observed in the boundary between waters of Palawan and Sabah, Malaysia in January 2005. By February, fish kills reached Rizal, Palawan, and by March to Quezon, Palawan. Incidents were attributed to prevailing winds and currents. Fishermen sources revealed having witnessed a red discoloration off the Quezon waters with dense floating algae. Local

fish affected were: flying fish, “*molmol*”, “*sagisi*”, “*isdang bato*” and “*solid*”.

On 17 March 2005, a Press Conference was held to update the public concerning the fish kills in Palawan. It was with relief that the team of Mayor Edward Hagedorn announced to the public that fresh fish was safe for consumption and that the causative organism, *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*, has not been reported as toxic to humans, and only kills fish by depleting the waters of oxygen (Fig. 2). As of today, apparently, the bloom is moving farther to the North of Palawan, as we received reports of similar events in these areas, which however need to be confirmed.

A recent follow-up study included the monthly distribution of chlorophyll-a obtained from satellite images from MODIS Aqua Level 2 data with 1 km resolution. High chlorophyll content ($\geq 0.5 \text{ mg/m}^3$) were observed in February, 2005 in west and southwest Palawan and proceeded to spread northwards by March, 2005 which by then covered a large portion of the western coast (310 km in length and 80 km in width). The intensity of the bloom lessened by April, 2005 which was then concentrated in the northern tip of Palawan. Sabah, Malaysia being only a few kilometers away from Palawan showed corresponding waxing and waning of chlorophyll values. It is possible that this particular *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* bloom in Palawan could have originated from Malaysian waters following the circulation pattern in South China Sea during this season [1].

Background on *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*

Cochlodinium polykrikoides Margalef is an unarmored dinoflagellate species belonging to the Family Gymnodiniaceae. It forms chains characterized by having a conical epitheca and a bilobed hypotheca. Single cells are ellipsoidal with a displaced cingulum. It is cosmopolitan in nature but found more commonly in warm-temperate and tropical waters [2].

Fig. 2. *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*, the non-toxic dinoflagellate observed to bloom during the fish kill in Puerto Princesa, Palawan on March 16, 2005.

It has been causing fish kills in Asia, particularly annual blooms in Japan since the 1970's, Korea in the 1980's and China in the 1990's [3-5]. Extensive economic losses were reported, the highest, in Korea, of US\$95.5M [6]. More recently, it has been blooming in South-east Asia. Blooms of *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* were reported in Sabah, Malaysia in the latter part of 2003, and in Brunei in February, 2004 (Taha, pers. comm.). The bloom in Sabah recurred in January of this year [7].

In the Philippines, it caused fish kills in Iligan Bay, Southern Philippines and Balayan Bay, Batangas in March and June of 2002, respectively (Fig. 1B). In Iligan Bay, the bloom spanned 2000 m by 500 m wide killing demersal and pelagic fishes while in Batangas it covered 7000 m by 300 m spreading from

Balayan Bay to Nasugbu killing mostly reef fishes [8, 9].

It could be theorized that blooms in Puerto Princesa were transported from Sabah where persistent blooms of this organism have been reported since January of this year. Summer months in the region are characterized by weak south-westerly winds. Such winds could have transported *Cochlodinium* cells from Sabah to Puerto Princesa.

The generally accepted mechanism on how *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* kills fish is by suffocation. Due to its dense concentration during a bloom, it competes with other marine organisms for oxygen. When *Cochlodinium* cells rupture and die, they produce a mucus-like substance that covers the gills of fish, causing damage which thereby enhances suffocation. The fish with damaged gills then abnormally produce mucus, furthering decrease of gas exchange in the gills [10].

Extensive experimentation on how to mitigate harmful algal blooms of this organism is being done in Korea, and include various water treatments: sophorolipid, loess, cocamidopropyl betaine (a surfactant) and clay [11]. Algicidal treatment include Bacillamide which was isolated from *Bacillus* sp. [12] and phlorotannins from the seaweed *Ecklonia kurome* [13].

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ISSHA President's Corner

NEWS

Happy New Year in 2006! Time is passing quickly as we make progress toward the 12th International Conference on Harmful Algae scheduled 4-8 September in Copenhagen. Check ISSHA's web site (<http://www.issha.org/>) for updates. In addition to the oral and poster sessions, break out groups and banquet, the Conference Organizers have added an auction to this year's meeting activities. From having attended the annual

PSA (Phycological Society of America) auctions, I can assure you the ISSHA auction will become a very popular part of our meetings as well. It is an opportunity for you to bring algal related memorabilia, books, monographs, reprints or copies of your best micrographs or SEMs of toxic (or non-toxic) cells (or you fill in the blank) and share these with colleagues throughout the world. Notify gerth@bi.ku.dk with your contributions and look forward to an evening of fun at the ISSHA Auction.

PUBLICATIONS

Physiological Ecology of Harmful Algal Blooms (1998) edited by Anderson, Cembella and Hallegraeff are now available from ISSHA for \$10 US (plus \$10 handling and shipping; recipient is responsible for any duty charges). Please contact Nina Lundholm (NLundholm@bi.ku.dk) to order copies. Payment must be made in DK or US\$ by cash or credit card (VISA or Master Card) only. The editors secured the

copyright to this volume and ISSHA is especially grateful for their generosity in allowing the Society to reproduce the original volume in a compact disc format. A quick check of the online availability and price of this volume listed 7 copies starting at prices over \$800 per copy.

For those of you who were not able to join us for the Xth International Conference on Harmful Algae in St. Pete Beach, FL, the Proceedings are available through FWRI website (http://www.floridamarine.org/features/view_article.asp?id=12373). To access the Proceedings, click on Red Tide under Research, then HAB Information Links under Harmful Algal Bloom Facts and Information.

AWARDS

Maureen Keller Student Awards were presented by ISSHA at the 11th Conference on harmful Algae held in Cape Town, South Africa. Please join me in congratulating these young researchers for their excellent oral presentations and posters.

Karen Arthur was awarded Best Presentation for her talk on "The Potential Exposure of Green Turtles to Tumour Promoting Compounds from the Cyanobacterium *Lyngbya majuscula*". Collaborators for this project were G. Shaw, C. Limpus, G. Balaza and J. Udy. Karen is a PhD candidate at the Centre for Marine Studies at the University of Queensland, Australia. Karen's current work focuses on marine turtles and their interaction with harmful algae; such as, *Lyngbya majuscula*, an alga causing extensive blooms responsible for overtaking seagrass beds that provide shelter and forage for large populations of green turtle and dugong. Karen has been fortunate in working with a number of marine turtle experts such as Dr. Colin Limpus (Queensland Parks and Wildlife Service, Australia) and George Balazs (Marine Turtle Research Group, National Marine Fisheries Service, Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center), and environmental toxicologist Dr. Glen Shaw (Centre for Environmental Toxicology, University of Queensland, Australia). Karen enjoys her research with marine turtles and believes "Turtles enchant all who come across them; they represent a link

between peoples of the world as they migrate across international borders and yet are so susceptible to human impacts, living the large majority of their lives in a relatively localized inshore habitat".

Nicholas Touzet received Honorable Mention for his talk on "Inter and Intra-specific Variability in Morphogenetics and Toxin Composition of *Alexandrium* spp. in Irish Coastal Waters". Collaborators for his project include J.M. Franco and R. Raine. Nicholas obtained his degree in Marine Science from Universite de Bretagne Occidentale in Brest and his Masters in Toxic Interactions in Ecosystems and Toxin Biotechnologies from the Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle in Paris. He is currently focused on the morphogenetics and toxin composition of *Alexandrium* species in Irish coastal waters. He conducts his research in Ireland at the Martin Ryan Institute located at the National University of Ireland, Galway and is part of the research team led by Dr. Robin Raine. Nicholas' plans for the future include participating in the EU 6th framework project SEED and eventually lecturing his research topic within third level institutions. Along with his academic achievements, Nicholas is also a sports fan and plays wing for the University rugby team. Congratulations Nicholas.

Pauliina Uronen received Best Student Poster for her work on "Transfer of Nodularin to the Copepod *Eurytemora affinis* Through the Microbial Loop". Collaborators for her project include P. Kuuppo, S. Sapanen, C. Svensen, C. Legrand, A. Ruhl, T. Tamminen, and E. Graneli. Pauliina is earning her PhD in Finland at the Tvärminne Zoological Station at the University of Helsinki and the Finnish Environment Institute. She has studied species such as *Nodularia spumigena*, *Prymnesium parvum* and *Dinophysis* spp. Her current focus is on harmful algae and the transfer of algal toxins in the aquatic food web, specifically, the harmful species occurring in the Baltic Sea. Pauliina remarked that the Maureen Keller Student Poster Award encouraged her to continue studies with harmful algae. In addition to Pauliina's academic agenda, she can also be found sailing in the Baltic Sea, hiking in nearby forests and spending time with close friends and family.

Patricia Blair was awarded Honorable Mention Student Poster for her work on "Algicidal Bacteria Targeting the Toxic Dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis*: The Importance of Interactions within the Microbial Community". Collaborators for this project include M. Twiner, C. Mikulski, K. Jones and G.J. Doucette. She graduated Magna Cum Laude from West Virginia University, USA with a BA in Biology and a BS in Environmental Protection. She then taught coastal ecology at The Marine Science Consortium for three years. She is pursuing her Masters of Marine Biology at the Grice Marine Laboratory at the University of Charleston, SC. Her current research focuses on characterizing the interactions between algicidal bacteria and the Florida red tide species *Karneia brevis*. She conducts her work in the lab of Dr. Gregory Doucette of the NOAA Marine Biotoxins Program at the nearby Center for Coastal Environmental Health and Biomolecular Research. When out of the lab, Patricia enjoys rowing for her college crew team and playing volleyball. When she completes her degree program, Patricia hopes to continue working in the harmful algal bloom field.

Pat Tester, ISSHA President.
December, 2005.

Harmful Algae News

Previous issues of HAN and newsletters of the IOC HAB Programme can be downloaded at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/news.htm>

Requests for subscription

Subscription to HAN is made by sending a request with a complete address to Ms V. Bonnet (v.bonnet@unesco.org).

REMEMBER TO RENEW YOUR MEMBERSHIP IN ISSHA – NOW DUE EVERY SECOND YEAR ONLY!

From now on, payment is due every second year. Next payment is due from Jan 1, 2006 and is for the years 2006-2007.

Hence the fees in 2006 (January 1-December 31) are:

- Regular members 40\$.
- Student members: 20\$.
- Institutional members 80\$.

If you want to avoid having to remember to pay the dues, please be aware that a Life Time Membership of ISSHA is possible for only \$500.

Remember that you get a registration discount for the 12th International Conference on Harmful Algae in Copenhagen, September 2006 when becoming a member in 2006.

New applications for membership may be made at any time during the year. If paying in 2006, 2008, etc. payments are the regular rates listed above. Payment in the years in between (2007, 2009, etc.) will only be for one year as is hence half the price indicated above.

Please note that the Society revenue is primarily derived from annual contributions paid by membership dues.

To pay, please complete the form on the web-page (www.issaha.org) and either renew or apply for membership.

PHYCOTOXINS

You can also get news on HAB research and events at the Phycotoxins-list at the internet.

The address of this list is: phycotoxins@www.agr.ca

To join the list, send "subscribe phycotoxins" to listserv@www.agr.ca

Archives are located at <http://www.agr.ca/archives/phycotoxins.html>

ISSHA AUCTION

At the 12th International HAB conference on Harmful Algae we will have an auction, the surplus of which will go to the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA). But in order to become a success we need your help with donation of various items. Only your imagination sets the limit for what can be donated. It could be signed reprints, books, photos or craftsmanship (paintings, drawings, carvings etc.), homemade wine, beer or other specialities.

At www.issaha.org you can already now see the items that have been donated for the auction. The auction catalogue will be updated regularly between now and the Conference.

If you want to make a donation please contact Gert Hansen (gerth@bi.ku.dk). We look forward to hearing from you.

The Organising Committee of the 12th International Conference on Harmful Algae.

Future events

FEBRUARY 2006

OCEAN SCIENCES MEETING
February 20-24, 2006. Honolulu, Hawaii.

Call for Abstracts Special HAB Session: Abstracts are requested for a special session on Harmful Algal Blooms: From Research to Management at the Ocean Sciences Meeting, convened by Gina Perovich (Perovich.Gina@epamail.epa.gov) and Quay Dortch (Quay.Dortch@noaa.gov). A description of the session and instructions for abstract submission are available at:

www.whoi.edu/redtide/announcements/special_session_OS080.html

JUNE 2006

ASLO SUMMER MEETING
June 4-9, 2006. Victoria, Canada.

The American Society for Limnology and Oceanography, the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae, American Fisheries Society, Aquatic Plant Management Society and the Society for Canadian Limnologists invite you to attend the ASLO Summer meeting in Victoria, British Columbia, Canada on June 4-9, 2006. The theme of the meeting is "Global Challenges for Oceanography and Limnology".

Further information at: www.aslo.org/forms/victoria2006.html

SEPTEMBER 2006

12th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HARMFUL ALGAE

September 4-8, 2006. Copenhagen, Denmark.

Call for submission of abstracts and registration form: February 1, 2006.

Deadlines:

- Abstracts reception: May 1, 2006
- Early registration: June 1, 2006
- Late registration: July 15, 2006

Further information can be found at: www.bi.ku.dk/hab/

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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